

Whitepaper — July 2025

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Abstract:

FLAME is a lightweight, domain-specific programming language (DSL) created for the modeling of wildfire behavior.

Its simplicity, Python-based interpreter, and open-source nature make it ideal for research, training, simulation, and

Key Features:

- Wildfire modeling syntax
- Real-time decision rule expression
- Integration with IPMA/SGIFR/FIRMS datasets
- Designed for use in civil protection and environmental analytics
- Open-source and extensible

Example Syntax (Flame DSL):

```
if NDMI < 0.3 and PIR == "Muito Elevado" then
  alerta "■ Extreme propagation risk"
end
```

Current Development:

- REST API integration
- Interactive Streamlit dashboards
- AI models using PyTorch for fire prediction
- Web playground

License: MIT

Status: Active Open Source Project

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